

AFTER THE POPULAR UPRISINGS OF 1916 NAMANGAN OVER UYEZDI RESIDENTS RELEASE OF A COURT SENTENCE

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Annotation: In this work provides brief information about the organizers and participants of the people's uprising, which rose in Namangan uyezdi as a result of the announcement of the 1916 fam of the Russian emperor on mobilization for labor, as well as the announcement of a judicial verdict over them.

Keywords: Zhiliboy Karimbayev, Yulduz Niyozmatov, Tokhtanazar Islambayev, Falcon Sharipov, Nabi Shodibayev, Mukhitdin Sarayev, stop Khalikbayev, Pansot Eshonsaid Burkhanov.

90 people were taken to the Hibs from the rebels in the village of Chodak, Namangan uyezdi. In the "criminal case" initiated by the prosecutor, they were accused of the following: Zhiliboy Karimboev, Turgun Niyozmatov, Nasriddinqori Muhammadaminhojayev and Vaqqoskhan Madalikoriyev, the elder of the village of Chodak, tried to punish Mirrajabov and the volost steward Mullagozi Khudoyberdiyev, accusing him of compiling a list of laborers. The crowd broke into the House of the volost chief Khudoyberdiyev, led by Zhiliboy Karimbayev, Turgun Niyozmatov, Nabi Shodiboyev. The previous ranks of the crowd included Zhiliboy Karimbayev, Turgun Niyozmatov, Abdusamad Abduraimov, Nabi Shodibayev, Abdusattor Abduraimov, Yulduz Niyozmatov, Tokhanazar Islambayev, Yunuspolvon Mirsharipov, Sharif Aminov, Nasriddinqazi Muhammadaminkhojayev, Yulguz Ashirmatov, Said Tashpolvanov, Madamin Mirziyoyev, Mukhitdin Sarayev, and qashkan madalikorievs who stood. They were thrown and shot at the volost Chiefs, and the crowd was also thrown at several ellik_boshis. They consisted of Shamat Tashbayev, Muyassar Nigmatova, Kholmat Dostmatov, Abdulkosim Madazimov and others.

Those who were taken to the Hibs: — Zhilibay Karimbayev (45 years old), Turgun Niyozmatov (55 years old), Abdusamad Abduraimov (31 years old), Nabi Shodibayev (55 years old), Abdusattor Abduraimov (36 years old), Yulguz Niyozmatov (28 years old), Tokhanazar Arslonbayev (32 years old), Toyirboy Khudoyorov (58 years old), Rachimboy shodiboev (67 years old), Kholmirza Kholmatov (46 years old), Falcon Sharipov (17 years old) and khakozos[1.16-17].

In this information it can be seen that the age of the insurgents was between the ages of 17 and 80. This suggests that in the uprising, representatives of all local residents, regardless of age, headed against the government. Among them, such women as Gulchanbibi Bobojonova, Norbibi Rozikova and Asalbibi Mirzaulugova were also sued. The military court was conducted under the chairmanship of Major General Abramov. And the members of the court consisted of Colonel Blinov and Lieutenant Colonel Dobrookhotov. For several days, the court continued its activities and sentenced Abdusamad Abduraimov, Biyos Zanliyev, Zhiliboy Karimboyev, Mulla Siroj Ma'zumov, Nabi Shodiboev, Asalbibi Mirzaulugova and others to confiscate and hang the property of a total of 22 people. However, the court made a separate decision to mitigate the death penalty, taking into account the fact that officials were killed in an emergency. Abdusattor Abduraimov, Ashirmat Raimdevonboev, Vaqqoskhan Madalikoriyev, Giyebullakhoja Govtov, Ergashkhoja Rakhziyev, Soyibkhoja Nazarkhojayev, Said Tashpolvonov, O'raqdevon Eshmatov, Ustaqosim Abdurasulov, Samad Tashboev and Yuldashmatov were released from the death penalty and exchanged for 10 years in exile.

Normirza Nosirov, Saidahmadhoja Daniel, Kholmira Kholmatorov and Tokhir Khudoyorov were sentenced to strict regime imprisonment and confiscation of property for a period of 4 years. Asalbibi Mirzaulugova was sentenced to 1 year in prison. Mullakoşak Raimbayev (36 years old), Mukhitdin Matkarimbayev (27 years old), Saidboy Khujamberdiyev (24 years old), Atamirza Boybobohojiyev (26 years old), Muhammad usta Khojiev (46 years old) were sentenced to hang and kill property[2.78-79].

Raimboy Saidboev (63 years old), Eshmatboy Khudoyberdiyev (33 years old), Madraim Bobokhojayev (28 years old), Abdurakhmonmazum Muhammadyusupov (58 years old), each sentenced to 12 years in a row. Other lambgolon participants were sentenced to 3 to 3 months in prison.

The trial of the insurgents in Namangan uyezdi ended in the following way.

1. In the trial of November 22, 1916, a court sentence is issued over stop Khalikboev and other total: 22kishi. According to the judgment of the court, 2 people were sentenced to Exile, 3 people to strict regime prison, 10 people to prison and 7 people were released.

2. During the trial in 1916, Zhiliboy Karimbayev and X.k. Total: 22The court will issue a verdict over the incident. According to him, 22 people were sentenced to death, 4 people were exiled, 6 people were imprisoned in strict regime, 28 people were imprisoned, 48 were released.

3. On November 24, 1916, the case of a total of 22 people, Mullakoşoq Rahimbayev and khakazo, was considered in court, and a court will judge them. According to him, 8 people were sentenced to death, 4 people in exile, 5 people in strict regime prison, 3 people in prison and 2 people were acquitted.

4. On December 8, 1916, Bekmurod Mulla Sarimanov and a total of 6 people are sentenced to trial. According to him, 3 people went into exile, 1 person to prison and 1 person was acquitted.

5. On December 9, 1916, a court ruled on the case of Turkhtarboy Mirzaboyev and a total of 19 people. According to the court sentence, 17 people were sentenced to the death penalty and 2 people were acquitted.

6. On November 16, 1916, a court verdict will be announced over Pansot Eshonsaid Burkhanov and a total of 50 people. According to him, 5 people were sentenced to hard-regime prison, 26 people to prison, and 19 people were acquitted.

7. On November 12, 1916, a court sentence of Kamolkhoja Eshonkhojaye and khakazo to a total of 80 people was read. According to the court sentence, 11 people were sentenced to death, 4 people to exile, 9 people to hard-regime prison, 22 people to prison and 32 people were acquitted[3.112-113].

8. On November 19, 1916, a court sentence on the case of Abdurakhman Rozikboev and khakazos a total of 19 people will be read. According to him, 4 people were imprisoned in a strict regime, 13 people were imprisoned, and 2 people were acquitted[4.113-114].

The above-mentioned death and exile penalty was later changed and somewhat mitigated.

The namangans tried to break the railways if they fought against the Tsarist government. Because military power would come through railways. Chunonchi, Koshqboy Rahmonberdiyev had placed four 1 Pood-weighted stones on the rails at the Newariq and Chortoq station on the Fergana railway. With this, he planned to overturn the fourth nameless train, but he was noticed by the guards and had time to stop the train.

After that, the case of Koshakboy Rahmonberdiyev was tried in a military court and sentenced to exile for a period of 15 years.

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